

New Cyanogen Derivatives of Molybdenum

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Manuscript received 4 July 1972; revised 3 July 1974; accepted 8 July 1974

CHEMISTRY of molybdenum has been the subject of immense interest in recent times due to its vital role in some biochemical reactions. In continuation of our work¹⁻³ on the chemistry of quinquivalent molybdenum we have extended our investigations to the cyanogen complexes of molybdenum in different oxidation states. The present communication deals with the isolation of two new cyanogen derivatives of mixed ligand type, $K_2[Mo(CN)_6L]$ (where $L=2,2'$ bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline) which have been isolated as pale brown crystalline solid and characterised by analytical and other physicochemical methods. Further work in this line is in progress which will be published in due course.

Experimental :

All reagents used were of AR grade. $K_4[Mo(CN)_8]$ was prepared by usual⁴ method. Molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically as MoO_3 after decomposing the sample with concentrated⁴ sulphuric acid and nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. Oxidation state of the metal was determined with ceric sulphate method and magnetic susceptibility measurement was made in Gouy balance.

Preparation :

About 1g. of the octacyanomolybdate $K_4[Mo(CN)_8]$, $2H_2O$ was dissolved in minimum quantity of water. The organic ligand (in the molar ratio 1 : 2) was dissolved in dilute acetic acid. When these two solutions were mixed together and stirred there was immediate precipitation of pale brown crystalline solid which was filtered in sintered gooch X'ble, washed with dehydrated ethanol and was finally dried to constant weight in vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. The product was obtained in about 70% yield.

Found : Mo, 19.74%, N, 22.67% ;

Calc. for $K_2[Mo(CN)_6.bipy]$, Mo, 19.75%, N, 23.04%

Found : Mo, 18.39% ; N, 21.60% ;

Calc. for $K_2[Mo(CN)_6.phen]$, Mo, 18.82%, N, 21.96%

Properties : Oxidation state of the metal in both these compounds was found to be four. These are diamagnetic as is expected from the d^4sp^0 hybridisation of these octa-coordinated complexes. These are soluble in water and show interesting colour reactions (precipitate) with different metal ions, Fe^{3+} (bluish green), Fe^{2+} (yellow), Cu^{2+} (violet), Co^{2+} (brownish yellow), UO_2^{2+} (reddish brown), MoO_4^{2+} (reddish brown), Cd^{2+} (pale yellow).

I. R. Spectra :

Infra-red spectra were taken in Beckman Infrared spectrophotometer in KBr phase. Both these compounds showed strong absorption at 2100 cm^{-1} which can be accurately assigned as cyanogen band⁵ ($\nu_{CN}=2100$). The other parts of spectra are different in two compounds. In $K_2[Mo(CN)_6.bipy]$ strong bands were obtained in the region 760 cm^{-1} which may be due to out of plane bending of ring hydrogens and the 1430 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} bands as ring frequency of the organic ligand. Except these there are numerous weak bands between $900-1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$. In $K_2[Mo(CN)_6.phen]$ strong bands were observed in three regions, $700-900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ weak bands between $1125-1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1400-1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The strong bands at 725 cm^{-1} and 850 cm^{-1} are probably associated with the coordinated phenanthroline nitrogens with the metal atom. However, the spectra are in well agreement with the observation of the previous workers⁶ on identical compounds.

Electronic spectra :

Ultraviolet and visible spectra of the compounds were taken in Hilger UVISPEK. The absorption spectra in aqueous solution are very much identical (Fig. 1) in $K_2[Mo(CN)_6.bipy]$ and $K_2[Mo(CN)_6.phen]$. In the 2,2'-bipyridyl complex three bands are obtained at 250 nm ($40,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), 320 nm ($31,250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 375 nm ($26,666\text{ cm}^{-1}$) with molar

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of $K_2[Mo(CN)_6 \text{ bipy}]$ (II) and $K_2[Mo(CN)_6 \text{ phen}]$ (I) in water.

extinction, $\epsilon=175$, $\epsilon=60$ and $\epsilon=32$ respectively. In 1,10 phenanthroline complex three bands are obtained at 310 nm ($32,258 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 350 nm ($28,571 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 400 nm ($25,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) with molar extinctions, $\epsilon=165$, $\epsilon=80$ and $\epsilon=44$ respectively. The assignment of the bands can be made on the basis of dodekahedral crystal field of this eight

coordinated quadrivalent molybdenum complex (d^0) where the d orbitals split⁷ in the four levels, $B_1(d_{x^2-y^2}) < A_1(d_{z^2}) < E(d_{xz}, d_{yz}) < B_2(d_{xy})$.

The 250 nm band in $K_2[Mo(CN)_6 \text{ bipy}]$ with $\epsilon=175$ and the 310 nm band in $K_2[Mo(CN)_6 \text{ phen}]$ with $\epsilon=165$ may be due to the transition $d^0(x^2-y^2) \rightarrow (d_{x^2-y^2})(d_{z^2})$. The other two transitions appearing as weak humps in the spectra with lower extinctions appear to be due to spinforbidden transitions.

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